

THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL NETWORKING ON STUDENTS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Abstract: Social Networking is a internet-based social spaces designed to facilitate communication, collaboration, and content sharing across networks of contacts. Social Networking Sites allow users to manage, build and represent their social networks online. Social Networking Sites are usually made up of other individuals; they might also include profiles of events, companies, even political parties. People use Social Networking Sites for countless activities. Social media generally refer to media used to enable social interaction. It is important to note the difference between user-generated content, which is non-traditional media developed and produced by individual users, and existing content, which is usually traditional media (news, magazines, radio, and television) reproduced for the web. In addition to these features, SMT also contains design elements that create virtual social spaces encouraging interaction, thereby broadening the appeal of the technology and promoting transitions back and forth from the platform to face-to-face engagement. The use of social media interfaces through computer and mobile devices has become quite widespread, and currently, the two most prominent interfaces are Face book and Twitter. Twitter is a social media interface that enables users to share a limited amount of user-generated content, quickly and easily, to an extensive number of other users. With this interface, the communication exchange is central, and the creation and sharing of user profiles is not necessary, but Twitter can link to user profiles that exist on other social media interfaces. The impact of social networking on students in higher education a study in Bangalore will be discussed in detail.

Keywords: Social networking, Social media, Facebook, Twittter, Higher Education, Students.

1. INTRODUCTION

Social Networking Sites can be broadly defined as **internet-based social spaces designed** to facilitate communication, collaboration, and content sharing across networks of contacts. Social Networking Sites allow users to manage, build and represent their social networks online. Social Networking Sites are usually made up of other individuals; they might also include profiles of events, companies, even political parties.

Social media [technology] has become a growing phenomenon with many and varied definitions in public and academic use. Social media generally refer to media used to enable social interaction. It is important to note the difference between user-generated content, which is non-traditional media developed and produced by individual users, and existing content, which is usually traditional media (news, magazines, radio, and television) reproduced for the web. social networking sites is used as an umbrella term for all social media and computer-mediated communication, including but not limited to Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, and Myspace, as well as the inaugural social networking sites of Cyworld, Bebo and Friendster.

Social Media Technology (SMT) refers to **web-based and mobile applications** that allow individuals and organizations to create, engage, and share new user-generated or existing content, in digital environments through multi-way communication.

TYPES OF SOCIAL NETWORKS

There are number of ways to categorize the available Social Networking Sites. While Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn might be the first sites that come to mind when There are number of ways to categorize the available Social Networking Sites. While Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn might be the first sites that come to mind when thinking of social networking. These popular websites do not represent the full scope of social networks that exist.

Categories of Social Networking Sites

Type	Definition	Examples
Social connections	Keeping in touch with friends and family members	Facebook, Google+, Twitter, Myspace
Media Sharing	Social networking makes it easy to share video and photography content online	Youtube, Flickr, Picasa
Professional	Professional social networks are designed to provide opportunities for career related growth	LinkedIn, Classroom 2.0
Informational	Informational Communities are made up of people seeking answers to everyday problems	Forums, Unlimited.com
Educational	Educational networks are where many students go in order to collaborate with other students on academic projects, to conduct research for school, or to interact with professors and teachers via blogs and classroom forums	Stackover flaow.com
Academic	Academic researchers who want to share their research and review by colleagues	Acadmia.edu

Adolescents use social media in large numbers. For example, a national survey in 2009 finds that 73% of online teenagers use SNS, which is an increase from 55% 3 years earlier (Lenhart, Purcell, Smith, & Zickuhr, 2010). That youth are connected to these global online communities is both a frightening prospect for parents and educators and an intriguing area for social science research. For example, educators and parents in the United States face difficult quandaries concerning students and SNS.

IMPACT OF SOCIAL NETWORKS ON EDUCATION

Education is very essential part of an individual's life for every teenager education is more important than anything. Today teenager shows very much interest for using social networks but unfortunately Social Networks affect education badly [3]. Previous research has calculated that more than 90% of college students use social networks [9, 10]. Technology has shown a fast development by producing small communication devices but these small communication devices can be used for accessing social networks any time anywhere, these devices include pocket computers, laptops, iPads and even simple mobile phones (which support internet) etc.

Positive Effects of Using Technology

Technology is step towards betterment, no doubt but any technology which can provide ease of social networks can be dangerous for social network addicts. Providing ubiquitous facility of social networks is a straight invitation of addiction to any teenager and even an adult, as academic satisfaction is not enough for those students who suffers from social isolation. Social Networks grab the total attention and concentration of the students and diverts them towards non educational, unethical and inappropriate actions such as useless chatting, time killing by random searching and not doing their jobs.

The applications include games, advertisements, and other online activities like online live television etc. User can use these applications free, so that's why gaming freaks and addicts use to play these games without any installation and any other formality any time anywhere, these free of cost pleasure destruct students from their education, and they do not concentrate on their education.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

To assess the social networking among the students in their Psychological Development and academic success.

THE EFFECT OF SOCIAL NETWORK SITES ON COLLEGE STUDENTS' SOCIAL CAPITAL

Moral panic is a common reaction to new forms of communication. The advent of television spawned fears of mass idiotization. Similarly, in the early 90s, critics held the diffusion of Internet as evidence of individuals' increasing alienation from society and public life. The story with social network sites (SNS) such as Facebook and MySpace is not any different. Unsafe disclosure of information, cyber bullying, addiction, risky behavior and contacting dangerous communities are but a few of the concerns raised in the media about the use of online social networks.

The impact of online social networks on social capital can be achieved in myriad ways. For instance, common interest groups can help users coordinate for collective action.

SOCIAL NETWORKS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

The importance of social media as platforms of social interaction, communication and marketing is growing. The rapid ascent of social media across society is a very clear signal that individuals, groups and institutions are rapidly changing their preferences of how they learn, communicate, collaborate and participate in society. The immediacy of interaction, from the simplest response to a Tweet on Twitter to a very thoroughly researched and presented blog post, underscore how pervasive the foundational elements of Web 2.0 design precepts and principles are influencing daily life worldwide today. For educational institutions this shift in communication channels, patterns and preferences have an immediate effect on a given college or universities' level of credibility with prospective students, and has a direct effect on how trusted they are over the long-term.

1) It's free

In reality, nothing is really free. We still have to pay for Internet and technology in our building, but our software costs have gone down significantly. As educators continuously have to deal with budget cuts, it is important that we use tools that do not have a cost on it. Safety is essential, but with teaching Internet safety, setting up certain sites, with a little hard work, the software costs nothing.

2) It cuts down on isolation

There are some programs in an off-site building. Some of the program serves 12 students and has two teachers. Every few years, this program is revisited and they ensure that teachers have an opportunity to move so that they have the ability to connect and learn from others. They are both connected through many teachers through social networks and the feeling of isolation has somewhat dissipated.

3) Building tolerance and understanding of cultural diversity

There are so many different cultures in the world and we only had read about them in books. There is so much of an opportunity to not only read content from different people and hear their perspectives, but social media gives us the opportunity to actually talk with people. Having the opportunity to connect with people all over the world breaks down a lot of barriers and builds understanding. These are opportunities that we did not have as kids but we need to ensure that our students have this opportunity now.

4) It can amplify passion

Passion is a term that has been used a great deal in education. We have to build learning upon the passions and interests of the students. We now have the opportunity to not only connect with people of different cultures, but to people with similar interests. A student talks about through the use of video, dance has evolved so rapidly because of the ease of sharing. The child who does not feel anyone has similar interests in the classroom, is not limited anymore. We can help to facilitate these connections in schools so our students do not only feel —normal, but their passion thrives.

5) The world of education is (and needs to be) more open

We need to continuously communicate and connect with not only the stakeholders, but the world of education. Parents no longer need to wonder what a teacher is thinking, because he can share it continuously in an open way. He can do everything from sharing his calendar for the week with the classroom community.

PRINCIPLES FOR GOOD PRACTICE RELATED TO STUDENT ENGAGEMENT

Chickering and Gamson (1987) proposed seven principles for good practice in undergraduate education, all of which are related to student engagement. They are: (1) student/faculty contact;

- (2) cooperation among students;
- (3) active learning;
- (4) prompt feedback;
- (5) emphasizing time on task;
- (6) communicating high expectations; and
- (7) respecting diversity.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Growing popularity and increasing usage of social media both academically and personally by the student community has led to a necessity for a comprehensive assessment of the psychological and personal issue of the students. Today, it is a premise that technology is an integral quotient for the student success equation. Traditional modes have taken a back seat as far socialization, learning and the like. The instant access, real time connectivity coupled with the impulsive behavior of the college students have led to multiple psychological and other issues. Social networking among the students is assuming greater relevance and catching up with the speed and velocity prompted by the teaching community across the globe.

The saga of social networking has revolutionized the learning and student engagement in India particularly in the higher education. There is a need to do a reality check on whether the social networking can supplement student engagement.

The present study becomes very relevant with psychological, student engagement and socio-cultural context and hence titled “**The Impact of Social Networking on Students in Higher Education**”.

The present study is based on the seven principles proposed by Chickering and Gamson (1987) for good practice in undergraduate education, all of which are related to student engagement.

They are:

1. Student/ faculty contact
2. Cooperation among students
3. Active learning
4. Prompt feedback
5. Emphasizing time on task
6. Communicating high expectations
7. Respecting diversity

While there is little research focusing on the relationship between social media and student engagement in higher education, a number of studies have found relationships between technology and engagement.

CHALLENGES FOR SOCIAL MEDIA USE

Though social media can increase student learning through student interactions, challenges arise when social media are incorporated into an academic course. The assumption that students are familiar with and agreeable to using certain types of social media can cause educators to inadvertently fail to provide the resources or encouragement necessary to support student usage and learning.

Social media can also be a challenging instructional strategy to incorporate because it attempts to balance the authority of the educator with the active participation of the students. Collaboration through social media supports more of a constructivist approach to learning, where students and educators can work together to co-create understanding of a particular topic, rather than an approach that emphasizes individual contributions (Stevens, 2009). As a result, students and educators become equal participants in the knowledge sharing process.

Though this seems beneficial for creating and disseminating knowledge, social media can also become a privacy concern (i.e. cyber-plagiarism) as well as an outlet for abuse and cyber-bullying (Chen & Bryer, 2012; Frye et al., 2010; Jackson, 2011; Smailes & Gannon-Leary, 2011). This suggests that establishing standards for social media use should include behavior and attitude guidelines similar to those enforced in the classroom.

2. CONCLUSIONS

The increasing number of research regarding social media and its use in different areas, most especially in education gives proof that it can lead to a significant change in how we structure learning spheres in the future. It has the potential to change the traditional relationship between teachers and students, thus giving more control and guidance to motivate students which can result in a more satisfactory learning experience. A growing number of educators are using the advantages social media offers in the classroom to engage into a more dynamic dialogue with students and other faculty members. Literally, the use of social media makes us to provide a new and innovative dimension in the whole educational process in order to enable student adapt to a future where everything rapidly evolves. Undoubtedly, it has created an E-Environment in the realm of New Age Education. An overwhelming majority report that they believe that Social Media Sites are valuable tools for teaching, and a majority report that Social Media Sites can be valuable tools for collaborative learning. It is an emphatic assertion that "Social Media Sites are not a part of our life; it is fully part of our living."

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